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Original Research

URINARY SCHISTOSOMIASIS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS IN AN URBAN COMMUNITY IN JOS-NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Urinary schistosomiasis is a neglected tropical disease caused by the parasitic worm *Schistosoma haematobium*. Although significant efforts have been made to control neglected tropical diseases, schistosomiasis continues to pose a major public health challenge in Nigeria. This study was conducted among primary school pupils in Anguwan Rogo community of Jos-North Local Government Area, Plateau State, Nigeria, to determine the status of urinary schistosomiasis. Between June and November 2020, 250 urine samples were collected from pupils in three primary schools. The samples were analysed for *S. haematobium* eggs using the standard sedimentation technique. The overall prevalence of *S. haematobium* was 4(2.0%) with infection observed only at L.E.A Primary School, Anguwan Rogo ($p < 0.05$). Only males (4.12%) acquired the infection while subjects aged ≥ 13 years accounted for the highest prevalence (7.9%) of the infection ($p < 0.05$). Although, there was no significant association ($p > 0.05$) between *S. haematobium* infection and water source, subjects who used well (3.4%) and tap (2.0%) as source of water accounted for the highest burden of the infection. Overall, it is concluded that although the prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis is low in this study, the finding highlights the need for targeted interventions and control measures to prevent transmission and protect vulnerable populations in urban areas.

Keywords: Urban communities, Urinary Schistosomiasis, Plateau State, Nigeria

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Urinary schistosomiasis, caused by the parasitic worm *Schistosoma haematobium*, is a significant public

health concern in many tropical and subtropical regions, especially in Africa and the Middle East (World Health Organization [WHO], 2023).

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The infection occurs through contact with freshwater contaminated by cercariae, the larval form of the parasite, which penetrate the human skin (WHO, 2023). Once inside the body, the parasites lodge in the venous plexus of the bladder, leading to symptoms such as hematuria (blood in urine), bladder fibrosis, and kidney damage (Colley *et al.*, 2014). Prolonged infection with urinary schistosomiasis can lead to severe complications, including an increased risk of bladder cancer (Zaghloul *et al.*, 2020). Chronic urinary schistosomiasis can also lead to underdiagnosed infertility issues and increase the susceptibility of infected individuals to HIV (van Tong *et al.*, 2017; Aula *et al.*, 2021; Okoroafor *et al.*, 2024). Globally, schistosomiasis affects millions, with over 90% of cases requiring treatment occurring in Africa (WHO, 2023). Current reports on urinary schistosomiasis in Nigeria, particularly in North Central Nigeria and Jos Plateau State, indicate a significant public health challenge (Aribodor *et al.*, 2024; Griswold *et al.*, 2022; Ejinaka *et al.*, 2022). A study in Kwara State found that 45.6% of school children were infected with urinary schistosomiasis. Infection rates were higher in males (50.8%) than in females (42.4%), with an average of 127.9 eggs per 10 ml of urine (Babamale *et al.*, 2018). The study identified key factors such as limited access to clean drinking water, unemployment and insufficient awareness and knowledge about the disease as key contributors to the high prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis. Another study by Dawet *et al.*

(2012) in Jos North Local Government Area found a significantly lower prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis, at 2.07%. Although Nigeria has seen a decline in urinary schistosomiasis prevalence in recent years (Onyekwere *et al.*, 2022; Obijiofor *et al.*, 2024), the risk of reinfection and transmission remains high in many areas. The overall situation in Nigeria and Plateau State suggests that urinary schistosomiasis remains a persistent public health threat with millions at risk. Continuous monitoring is crucial to identify affected areas and effectively control the spread of the disease.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The research was conducted in the Anguwan Rogo community of Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria (Fig. 1). Plateau State is located in the Northern Guinea Savannah vegetation belt, covering 8600 km² with an average altitude of 1280 metres. It lies between latitude 9° 55' N 8° 54' E. The climate is semi-temperate with temperatures ranging from 18^oc (64.4^oF) to 25^oc (77.00f). Jos receives about 1400mm (55.1 in) of rainfall annually.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing Anguwan Rogo in Jos North Local Government Area (Generated using QGIS version 3.38.3)

2.2 Sample Size Determination

The sample size for this study was determined using the Cochran formula described by Naing et al. (2006), with an established prevalence estimate of 2.07% (Dawet et al., 2012):

$$N = \frac{Z^2 P}{1-P} / d^2 \text{-----Equation 1}$$

$Z = 1.96$, $p = 2.07\%$ (0.0207) is the expected prevalence according to a previous study in the same LGA, d is the precision or margin of the error (5%, $d = 0.05$), and N represents the sample size. A minimum sample size of 31 was obtained. However, the sample size obtained was adjusted to 200 as the baseline sample size of our study to avoid bias in the selection of the school children.

2.3 Sample Collections

The study was conducted among pupils of three (3) primary schools within the study community. Pupils were randomly selected based on age, sex, and water source without bias. Clean and sterile urine containers (bottles) were given to each of these pupils so that they could collect 10–20 ml samples of mid-day urine for the study under the proper guidance of the teachers. The essential data of pupils such as names, age, sex, water source, sample number, time of collection, and names of schools were noted and recorded on the containers and laboratory request forms with the same information which was accompanied to the laboratory for investigation not later than two hours of collection as described by Abubakar et al. (2022).

2.4 Laboratory Processing and Microscopic Examination of Urine Samples

During the laboratory investigation, visible haematuria in one of the samples was noted and recorded. The urine centrifugation and sedimentation technique (WHO, 2023) was employed to analyse the urine samples. 10 ml of urine was taken from the deposit of each sample bottle after allowing it to sediment for 1 hour and centrifuged for 5 minutes at 2000 rpm. On a grease-free slide, a drop of detached deposits of the urine sample was placed and covered with a cover slip gently to avoid the formation of air bubbles. Each slide was viewed independently under the microscope at X10 and X40 objectives for the characteristic *Schistosoma haematobium* eggs or ova. The eggs are light yellow-brown and contain a conspicuous terminal spine as described by Agrawal Kumar (2022).

2.5 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

All pupils who had lived in the area for at least six (6) months and consented to the study were included. Whereas those who declined to give their consent for the study were excluded from the study.

2.6 Data Analysis

The data generated from the study was entered into Excel for cleaning and coding and thereafter imported into SPSS version 20.0 for statistical analysis. The Chi square test of association was used to ascertain if there was a significant difference between the prevalence of *Schistosoma haematobium* infection and the different variables that were studied. Results were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Results

Prevalence of *Schistosoma haematobium* Infection Across the Three Schools Sampled in Anguwan Rogo, Jos North, Plateau State

In this study, 200 primary school pupils in Anguwan Rogo, Jos North Local Government Area were investigated for the presence of *Schistosoma haematobium* infection. Table 1 shows that of the 200 pupils examined, 4(2.0%) were found positive for *Schistosoma haematobium* infection (see Plate 1 for the ova). The record of infection (4, 4.0%) was observed only at the Local Education Authority (L.E.A) Primary School Anguwan Rogo. There was however no infection observed at Hayatul Islam Primary School, and at Comprehensive Primary School, Jos North. Statistical analysis revealed that there was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the number of pupils infected with *S. haematobium* infection across the sampled schools in this study.

Table 1: Overall status of *Schistosoma haematobium* infection among Primary School Pupils in Anguwan Rogo Jos, Jos North, Plateau State

Study area	No. Examined	No. Infected	Prevalence (%)
L.E.A. Ang. Rogo	100	4	4.0
Tetengi Comp. Primary School	50	0	0.0
Hayatul Islam Primary School	50	0	0.0
Total	200	4	2.0

$$\chi^2 = 184.615, df = 2, p < 0.001$$

Prevalence of *Schistosoma haematobium* in Relation to Sex of Pupils in Anguwan Rogo, Jos North, Plateau State

There was a statistical relationship between the sexes of pupils with *Schistosoma haematobium* (Table 2).

In the current study, *S. haematobium* infection was detected only in the male pupils (4, 4.12%) with no record of infection (0%) in the female subjects as contained in Table 2. Chi square test revealed that males were significantly ($p < 0.05$) more infected compared to females who had no infection.

Table 2: Association of Sexes with *Schistosoma haematobium* Infection in Pupils in Anguwan Rogo, Jos North, Plateau State.

Sex	No. Examined	No. Infected	Prevalence (%)
Female	103	0	0.0
Male	97	4	4.12
Total	200	4	2.0

$$\chi^2 = 4.334, df = 1, p = 0.037$$

Prevalence of *Schistosoma haematobium* in Relation to Age of Primary School Pupils in Anguwan Rogo, Jos North, Plateau State

years old was infected while the remaining age groups sampled had no record of infection as contained in Table 3. Statistical analysis showed that there is a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection across the different age groups of the pupils sampled.

Across the different age groups sampled, pupils who were aged 13 years and above had the highest infection rate, 3 (75.0%). Only 1 (1.0%) pupil aged 10 – 12

Table 3: Association of Age Groups with *Schistosoma haematobium* Infection in Pupils in Anguwan Rogo, Jos North, Plateau State

Age group (years)	No. examined	No. infected	Percentage infected (%)
4-6	15	0	0.0
7-9	42	0	0.0
10-12	105	1	1.0
≥ 13	38	3	7.9
Total	200	4	2.0

$$\chi^2 = 8.4881, df = 3, p = 0.037$$

Association between *Schistosoma haematobium* infection and Water Source Among Pupils in Anguwan Rogo, Jos North, Plateau State

Table 4 shows the association between *S. haematobium* infection and water source. Infection

was encountered only in pupils who use well and tap as their sources of water. Higher infection (3.4%) was recorded in subjects who use well as their source of water compared to those that use tap (2.0%). However, statistical analysis revealed that the difference observed was not significant (> 0.05).

Table 4: Water Sources Associated With *Schistosoma haematobium* Among Pupils In Anguwan Rogo, Jos North, Plateau State.

Water source	No. examined	No. infected	Percentage infected (%)
Well	29	1	3.4
Tap	152	3	2.0
Borehole	14	0	0.0
River/Stream	5	0	0.0
Total	200	4	2.0

$$\chi^2 = 0.6986, df = 3, p = 0.874$$

Plate 1: Photomicrograph of *Schistosoma haematobium* ova (400X)

3.2 Discussion

Schistosoma haematobium is a neglected tropical disease prevalent in Nigeria. The disease is common among rural dwellers who reside around riverine areas or who have constant contacts with contaminated fresh water bodies. Although more prevalent in children and

adolescent, *S. haematobium* infection can infect individuals of all age groups (Wilczyńska et al. 2025; Gambo et al., 2021; Deribew et al., 2022). The current study was undertaken to ascertain the prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection among some primary school pupils in Anguwan Rogo, Jos North, Plateau State.

The overall prevalence of *S. The haematobium* infection recorded in this study was 2% (n=4) with pupils from L.E.A Anguwan Rogo being the only infected pupils. This is similar to the previous study by Dawet *et al.* (2012) who also reported a prevalence of 2.09% (n=5) in a study conducted at Kabong and Gwong Areas of Jos North Local Government Area. Another study by Akinboye *et al.* (2010) and Onyekwere *et al.* (2022) reported an overall prevalence of 9.2% (n=8) out of the 205 students examined in Ibadan North, Oyo State and between 4.6% in Eastern Nigeria to 15.9% in Western Nigeria respectively. Other studies, however, have reported higher prevalence compared to what was recorded in this study. For instance, Dahal *et al.* (2023) reported a prevalence of 16.3% in Jos while Damen *et al.* (2018) reported a prevalence of 18.7% in their study. While Ojo *et al.* (2021) reported prevalence as high as 58.5% in Northeast Nigeria. As previously observed by Dahal *et al.* (2023), the low prevalence of *S. haematobium* observed in this study could be due to differences in the study population, and the availability of freshwater bodies which could be infested by the intermediate host (*Bulinus* snails). Furthermore, the low prevalence in this study could be linked to the intervention by the government by regularly deworming with praziquantel (40mg/kg) as advocated by the World Health Organisation (WHO), but such intervention has been non-existent for many years, and school pupils depend on their parents and occasional Free Medical Outreach in their communities to get dewormed.

The only recorded infection in the current study was from L.E.A Primary School, Anguwan Rogo. This could be because it is a public school; therefore, sanitation and good hygiene are not maintained, and sufficient water facilities are not provided compared to the private schools so children are permitted to play nearby and come into contact with sources of infection. Similar to our finding Dahal *et al.* (2023) reported that prevalence varied between schools in their study and cited the availability of abandoned mining ponds, practices such as clothes washing, irrigation farming, and swimming are factors that favours the transmission of the disease in such schools. They also noted that low prevalence in other schools was accounted for by the presence of good water sources and toilet facilities with no abandoned ponds within the vicinity of the schools. This is similar to the findings of the current study where pupils in private schools were found with no infection, which could be due to the hygienic environment of the school.

Across gender, only male pupils were encountered with the infection in this study. None of the female

subjects sampled was infected with *S. haematobium* infection. Previous studies conducted by Nanvyat *et al.* (2011) and (Obijiofor *et al.*, 2024) also showed that males were more infected with prevalence rates of 56.7% and 24.0% respectively, compared to females with 25.8% and 11.1% rates of infection, respectively. A similar work by Balogun *et al.* (2022) also showed that males had a higher infection rate, 63.3% of the infected pupils were males compared to females who accounted for 36.7% of the infected population. Elsewhere in Yemen and Ethiopia, Alansi *et al.* (2025) and Woldeyohannes *et al.*, 2021 both reported higher prevalence in males than in females as well. While Dogara *et al.* (2020) reported the prevalence of 15.10% in male subjects which was higher than the 1.70% in the females. These findings are consistent with the result of the current study highlighting the role of gender-specific behaviors and exposure patterns in shaping the epidemiology of urinary schistosomiasis. Contrary to the result of this study however, Chukwu *et al.* (2013) reported a prevalence of 0.90% in female subjects with none of the males infected out of the 261 students' samples examined. Furthermore, Ayabina *et al.*, 2021 reported studies that had higher prevalence in females than in males.

The recorded prevalence in the male pupils in this study could result from the different playing habits of male and female children which include swimming, running in the waterways, and defecating in undesignated areas, which makes *S. haematobium* transmission easier. Moreover, females are more protected and are not always allowed to go outside, making them less vulnerable to the disease since this is a Muslim-dominated area.

In respect to age, pupils aged ≥ 13 had the highest rate of infection, (3,7.9%) followed by those aged between 10 – 12 years, 1(1.0 %). Similar to this finding, Dahal *et al.* (2023) also reported higher prevalence in subjects aged 11-13 years. Contrary to this finding, however, Umoh *et al.* (2020) reported higher prevalence in subjects aged 6-10 years old in their study. It is likely that the higher infection encountered in this age group could be related to the active playing habits of pupils within this age bracket which exposes them to the risk of contracting the infection. Pupils in the lesser age groups were found without man infection most likely because they are usually under the care of their parents/guardians or teachers at school and may not be so exposed to contaminated environments where they could easily acquire the infection.

In the current study, there was a significant association between urinary schistosomiasis and water source. Although, infection was observed in subjects

who use tap and well only as their sources of water, higher infection was observed in those that used well. Other water sources were not associated with *S. haematobium* infection in this study. Contrary to this study, Reuben *et al.* (2013) in a study conducted among secondary school students in Lafia, Nassarawa State, reported a significantly high infection (22.6%) in subjects who source water from stream. Similarly, Nguwoh *et al.* (2022) and (Onosakponome *et al.*, 2023) also reported higher infection in students who source water from stream/river followed by those that use tap in Cameroon and Bassa LGA in Plateau state, Nigeria respectively. However, Jacob *et al.* (2025) recorded infection only in subjects who use rain alongside other water sources but found no infection in subjects who use other water sources alone. Daribew *et al.* (2025) on the other hand recorded higher infection in those sources of water was river followed by well.

It is further observed in this study that due to the proximity of the study area to River Dilimi, which could be a suitable breeding ground for the *Scistosoma* vectors harbouring the parasites and the playing habits of these children around these places particularly after school hours, they could have been exposed to the infection from this place. In addition, other water related activities such as laundry could have been another source of exposure to these parasites.

4.0 Conclusion

The current study in Anguwan Rogo, Jos, Plateau State, found a notable prevalence of urinary schistosomiasis among primary school children, particularly among males aged from 13 years and above. The findings highlight the need for improved access to safe water, enhanced hygiene and sanitary practices, and targeted prevention and control measures in the area, especially in public schools. This will necessitate that adequate sanitary facilities and safe water be provided in these schools. Additionally, awareness programs should educate children, parents, guardians, and teachers about the transmission dynamics of *S. haematobium* infection, the risk factors associated with its transmission and prevention strategies to promote a healthier environment.

Author's Contribution

NN and GNM conceptualized and designed the study. GMN and GJG participated in fieldwork and data collection. AJA and BKL performed the laboratory and data analysis. NN and GMN drafted the manuscript, DAD reviewed it, and all authors

contributed to the final version and approved its submission.

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Nil.

Declaration

We declare that there is no any potential competing interest and that all authors have approved this manuscript for publication.

Ethics Approval and Informed Consent

This study was approved by the Jos University Teaching Hospital Institutional Research Ethics Committee (JUTH/DCS/IREC/127/XXX1/2357). We obtained consent from the headmasters of participating primary schools and informed all participants about the study's objectives.

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